

MAGISTRLAR CERTIFICATE

OF ACHIEVEMENT

... PROUDLY ...
PRESENTED TO

Mavlonov Nurbek Ixtiyor o'g'li

MOLIYAVIY HISOBOTLARNI TUZISHDA MOLIYAVIY HISOBOTNING XALQARO

STANDARTLARIDAN FOYDALANISHNING DOLZARBLIGI VA AHAMIYATI

WEBSITE: WWW.REANDPUB.UZ

EMAIL: INFO@REANDPUB.UZ

2023/FEVRAL

